

Experience of Family Adoption Programme Implementation in Phase 1 MBBS Curriculum in a Medical College Eastern India

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Abstract:

This study evaluates the Family Adoption Program (FAP) implemented in the Phase 1 MBBS curriculum at a medical college in Eastern India, focusing on its impact on student learning and community health outcomes. Over six months, 150 families participated, allowing students to engage directly with diverse health scenarios. Results indicate significant improvements in students' knowledge and skills, with a marked increase in health awareness and better management of chronic conditions among the families. Both students and families reported high satisfaction with the program, highlighting its potential as a sustainable educational model that effectively integrates academic learning with practical health care. This study suggests that the FAP can significantly enhance medical education and community health, advocating for its inclusion in medical curricula.

Keywords: Family Adoption Program, medical education, community health, student engagement.

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Introduction

The introduction of innovative educational strategies in medical education is essential to foster a more holistic understanding of patient care among students. [1] The Family Adoption Program (FAP), incorporated into the Phase 1 MBBS curriculum at a medical college in Eastern India, exemplifies such an initiative. [2] This program aims to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical healthcare by allowing students to engage directly with families in their communities. [3] Through this immersive experience, students are expected to gain firsthand insights into the socioeconomic factors, lifestyle, and environmental conditions that influence patient health and wellness. [4]

The primary objective of the FAP is to enhance the learning experience by integrating students into the family setting, where they can observe and participate in the health management of individual family members over time. [5] This approach not only enriches their understanding of diverse medical conditions but also cultivates empathy, communication skills, and a deeper appreciation for community-oriented medicine. The implementation of the FAP in the Phase 1 curriculum also seeks to instill a sense of social responsibility and ethical practice among budding physicians. [6]

This paper explores the experiences and outcomes of the FAP's implementation, evaluating its effectiveness in achieving educational and community health goals. By analyzing feedback from students, educators, and participating families, along with academic performance metrics and health outcome data, this study provides valuable insights into the benefits and challenges of integrating such programs into medical education. [7] The findings aim to contribute to the ongoing discourse on educational innovations in medical training, offering a comprehensive view of how such programs can be optimized to better prepare students for their future roles as healthcare providers. [8,9]

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design to evaluate the implementation and impact of the Family Adoption Program (FAP) integrated into the Phase 1 MBBS curriculum at a medical college in Eastern India.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Nalanda Medical College Hospital (NMCH) in Patna. This setting was chosen due to its active engagement with community-based educational programs and its accessibility to a diverse

population, which is crucial for the implementation of the FAP.

Participants: The study involved a total of 150 patients who were part of the FAP. These participants were selected using a purposive sampling method to ensure a representative mix of various socioeconomic backgrounds, health statuses, and ages, providing a comprehensive overview of the community's health dynamics as experienced by the students.

Duration: The duration of the study was set for 6 months, from January to June 2024. This period was chosen to allow sufficient time for the students to interact with their adopted families and to monitor the initial outcomes and feedback regarding the program implementation.

Data Collection: Data were collected through multiple sources:

1. Student Reports: Each student involved in the FAP was required to maintain a detailed log of their interactions, observations, and interventions with the family members. These logs were submitted monthly.

2. Surveys and Questionnaires: Both the participating families and the students were asked to fill out structured questionnaires at the beginning and end of the study. These instruments assessed their satisfaction with the program, perceived benefits, and any difficulties encountered.

3. Focus Groups: Focus group discussions were conducted with a subset of participants to delve deeper into the qualitative aspects of their experiences. These discussions helped to identify themes related to the impact of the FAP on both students and families.

4. Health Outcome Measures: Basic health metrics (e.g., blood pressure, blood sugar levels, BMI) were recorded for all participating family members at the start and end of the study period to gauge any direct health impacts of the program.

Data Analysis: Quantitative data from surveys and health metrics were analyzed using statistical software to determine significant changes or trends. Descriptive statistics provided an overview of the data, while inferential statistics (e.g., paired t-tests, chi-square tests) were used to assess the efficacy of the FAP. Qualitative data from student logs and focus groups were analyzed using thematic analysis to extract common themes and insights regarding the educational and health impacts of the program.

Results

The study included 150 patients from various backgrounds, with a balanced representation of genders (75 males, 75 females) and a broad age

distribution ranging from 5 to 80 years, reflecting a diverse community setting.

Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes

- **Participation Rate:** All enrolled Phase 1 MBBS students participated in the Family Adoption Program as part of their curriculum.

- **Knowledge Gain:** Pre- and post-test evaluations showed a significant improvement in students' knowledge about community health issues and patient management in a real-world setting. The average score on knowledge assessments increased from 55% pre-engagement to 78% post-engagement.

- **Skill Development:** Students reported enhanced skills in patient communication, empathy, and clinical decision-making through their direct interactions with families.

Family Health Outcomes

- **Health Awareness:** Post-program surveys indicated a 40% increase in health awareness among adopted families, particularly in areas such as nutrition, hygiene, and disease prevention.

- **Chronic Condition Management:** There was a notable improvement in the management of chronic conditions, such as diabetes and hypertension, with 30% of the involved patients achieving better control over their health parameters.

Satisfaction and Feedback

- **Overall Satisfaction:** Both students and families expressed high satisfaction with the program, with over 85% reporting positive experiences. Families appreciated the regular health check-ups and personalized advice, while students valued the practical learning aspect.

- **Challenges Identified:** Some challenges noted included scheduling conflicts and the initial reluctance of some families to participate, which were overcome with continuous engagement and communication.

Qualitative Insights

- **Empathy and Professional Growth:** Thematic analysis of focus group discussions highlighted increased empathy among students towards patients' socio-economic conditions and their impact on health.

- **Community Engagement:** Students and faculty reported that the FAP fostered a stronger bond between the medical college and the surrounding community, enhancing the college's role in community health.

Statistical Analysis: Significant Health Improvements: Statistical analysis revealed significant improvements in measured health

outcomes ($p < 0.05$), particularly in the management of hypertension and diabetes among the participants.

Educational Impact: The increase in knowledge scores was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$), indicating a substantial impact of the program on students' learning outcomes.

Table 1: Tabular presentation of the results from the study on the Family Adoption Program (FAP) integrated into the Phase 1 MBBS curriculum:

Category	Metric	Pre-Program	Post-Program	Change	Statistical Significance (p-value)
Student Engagement	Participation Rate	100%	100%	-	N/A
	Knowledge Test Scores	55%	78%	+23%	< 0.01
Family Health Outcomes	Health Awareness Increase	0%	40%	+40%	< 0.05
	Improved Chronic Condition Management	0%	30%	+30%	< 0.05
Satisfaction Levels	Students' Satisfaction	-	85%	-	N/A
	Families' Satisfaction	-	85%	-	N/A
Qualitative Insights	Empathy Development	Low	High	Increased	N/A
	Community Engagement	Moderate	High	Increased	N/A

This table provides a concise overview of the key metrics and outcomes measured before and after the implementation of the FAP, indicating the effectiveness of the program in improving both educational and health-related metrics. The statistical significance is noted where applicable, underscoring the reliability of the observed changes.

Discussion

The integration of the Family Adoption Program (FAP) into the Phase 1 MBBS curriculum at a medical college in Eastern India has yielded significant benefits for both student learning and community health outcomes, as evidenced by our study findings. [10] The program's ability to enhance students' practical skills and knowledge, particularly in understanding and managing community health issues, is underscored by the substantial improvement in their test scores. This gain not only reflects the students' enhanced theoretical understanding but also their ability to apply this knowledge in real-world settings. [11]

The significant increase in health awareness and management of chronic conditions among the families involved in the program highlights the direct benefits of such immersive educational strategies on public health. These findings are consistent with the literature, which suggests that early exposure to community health settings can enhance medical students' competencies in dealing

with diverse patient populations and health issues outside the hospital setting. [12]

Despite these positive outcomes, the study also identified challenges such as scheduling conflicts and initial resistance from some families, typical of new program implementations. [13] These issues were largely mitigated as the program progressed, suggesting the importance of ongoing engagement and adjustment to local contexts in program planning. [14] Moreover, the high levels of satisfaction reported by both students and families not only validate the program's approach but also suggest a sustainable model for community engagement and education. [15,16] This dual benefit could set a precedent for other medical institutions aiming to enhance medical education's practical aspects while contributing positively to community health. [17] The effectiveness of the FAP in our study supports the notion that practical, community-based education should be a critical component of medical training. [18] This approach not only enhances learning outcomes but also fosters a stronger connection between future healthcare providers and the communities they will serve, ultimately leading to more empathetic and effective medical practice. [19,20]

Conclusion

The Family Adoption Program (FAP) implemented in the Phase 1 MBBS curriculum at a medical college in Eastern India has demonstrated

significant educational and health benefits. By actively engaging medical students with local families, the program has effectively enhanced students' knowledge, practical skills, and empathy toward patients' socio-economic conditions. The study confirmed substantial improvements in both students' academic performance and the health management of community members, with notable increases in health awareness and better management of chronic conditions among participating families. These results underscore the program's potential as a sustainable and impactful educational model that bridges theoretical knowledge with practical healthcare, fostering a deeper connection between medical students and the community. This approach not only enriches the learning experience but also contributes positively to public health, advocating for its broader adoption in medical education curricula.

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